

glucose moiety was present at 3-position¹. In the pmr spectrum of the acetate the signals over the range δ 3.9–5.6 accounted for seven protons of the glucosyl residue. One of these a doublet centred at δ 5.14, was assigned to the C₁'-proton. The large coupling constant (J 7.5Hz) due to transaxial coupling with the C₂'-proton indicated the presence of β -configuration. Compound-A was thus characterised as quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucoside.

Compound-B: Pale yellow needles, m.p. 237°, gave positive Shinoda test and Molish test. Acid hydrolysis (6% aqueous HCl) afforded quercetin and D-galactose. The pmr spectrum (60 MHz, DMSO-d₆) of the glycoside, in addition to typical signals for quercetin skeleton, exhibited seven galactosyl protons. Thus it was a monogalactoside. The position of sugar was determined by studying the uv spectral data of the hydrolysed product of the permethylated glycoside using diagnostic shift reagents. A bathochromic shift of 61 nm in band-I absorption with AlCl₃ indicated that the sugar moiety was linked at 3-position¹. Enzymic hydrolysis of the glycoside with almond emulsin gave galactose showing β -linkage⁸. Thus it was characterised as quercetin-3-O- β -D-galactoside.

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Triterpenes from *Hoya parasitica*

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A number of triterpene alcohols, their acetates and cinnamates, anthocyanins, phenolic acids, flavonoids, acylated flavonoids and their glycosides besides β -sitosterol have been reported earlier from various *Hoya species*¹. Literature survey revealed that no work has yet been reported on *Hoya parasitica* (family: Asclepiadaceae) which is a creeper

growing on either of the two host plants, *Polyalthia longifolia* Thw. or *Pithecolobium saman* Benth. The present communication reports the isolation of a 3,4-seco acid of the lupane series besides lupeol and lupeone.

Air-dried, milled stem of *H. parasitica* Wall. growing on *Polyalthia longifolia* collected locally was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with light petrol. The residue left after removal of the solvent was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution was extracted with 1% aqueous caustic potash solution. The aqueous alkaline phase on acidification yielded a solid (0.04%) which was crystallised from methanol to give the pure seco-acid, m.p. 208–12°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +64.4^\circ$ (c 0.132 in CHCl₃). Its homogeneity was checked by tlc. It gave violet colour in the Liebermann–Burchard test.

The ms of the compound recorded the molecular-ion peak at m/z 442 which corresponds to the molecular formula C₃₀H₅₀O₂. Its ir (KBr) and ¹H nmr (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) data revealed the presence of a carboxylic acid group [ν_{\max} 3 600–3 400 and 1 710 cm⁻¹; δ 9.37 (1H, br, exchangeable with D₂O)], an isopropenyl group² [ν_{\max} 1 640 and 882 cm⁻¹; δ 1.73 (3H, s), 4.77 and 4.65 (1H, d each, J 3Hz)], and six additional methyls [δ 1.1 and 1.0 (3H, s each), 0.93–0.77 (12H, ill-resolved)]. The above data clearly revealed that it was a triterpene acid. On treatment with diazomethane it furnished a monomethyl ester (ν_{\max} 1 740 cm⁻¹) as an amorphous solid, having molecular ion peak at m/z 456, commensurate with the molecular formula C₃₁H₅₂O₂. Besides showing peaks at m/z 427 (M -Me)⁺, 399 (M -Pr)⁺, 257, 218, 217, 203 and 189, the ms of the acid recorded two important peaks at m/z 369 (a) and 223 (b) which are typical of 3,4-seco-lupene and -hopene derivatives³. Further, the appearance of two separate signals as (1H, d each) rather than of a (2H), broadened signal around δ 4.7 indicated⁴ that the compound belongs to the lup-20(29)-ene skeleton.

All the above data, considered together, clearly showed that the acid is 3,4-seco-lup-20(29)-en-3- α -oic

acid (1). This assignment was verified by comparison of and similarity in the spectral data (ir and ms) of its methyl ester (2) with those reported⁵ for the same compound isolated earlier from the plant *Caralluma bucharidii* (family: Asclepiadaceae). It, however, occurred as the methyl ester, and not as the free acid, in the plant.

The seco acid has earlier been reported⁶ from the sediments of a river bed in Indonesia. However, no data whatsoever were reported for the compound. Moreover, the structural assignment was based on identical gc run and similar ms data of its derived methyl ester and a semi-synthetic sample. But it is established that ms data cannot distinguish between the lupane and the hopane series. Also, it was not stated anywhere in the report if the gc conditions employed can distinguish between the two said triterpenoid classes. Our present work, therefore, fully characterises for the first time the seco acid as such from nature and also constitutes the first report of its occurrence in the plant kingdom.

From the non-acidic part of the petrol extract were isolated by preparative tlc lupeol and lupenone, which were identified by comparison (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc, ms) with authentic samples. The co-occurrence of lupenone and the corresponding 3,4-seco acid provides further support to the suggested biogenesis⁶ of the latter by photochemical (or photomimetic) conversion from the corresponding 3-keto precursors.

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Gravimetric Determination of Mercuric Ions by Precipitation with 2-Thioorotic Acid (Amm. Salt)

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2-THIOOROTIC acid (1) has shown a good complexing behaviour with a number of metal ions¹⁻³. It forms a white, stable, sparingly soluble complex, $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$. The reaction is quantitative, and the precipitate is filterable after the reaction.

1

Experimental

Solution of ammonium salt of 2-thioorotic acid (Eastman Kodak) (3.44 g) was prepared by heating it with minimum volume of concentrated ammonia solution to obtain a clear solution. Insoluble particles, if any, were removed by filtration. The solution was evaporated nearly to dryness and dried in an oven at 110° for 1 h and then dissolved in distilled water, and made upto 250 ml. A series of mercuric chloride solutions was prepared by weighing 5–400 mg of the compound (AnalaR, 99.5%), and dissolving each in about 25 ml distilled water.

Procedure: To the mercuric salt solution, potassium chloride (AnalaR) (~500 mg) was added, and warmed to 60°. The precipitating solution was added slowly with constant stirring. A white precipitate was formed which settled down in 5–10 min; a few drops of the solution were added further to ensure complete precipitation. The reaction mixture was digested on a water-bath for 30 min. It was then cooled, filtered through a sintered crucible (G-4), and washed with hot water till free from chloride ions (washings tested with AgNO_3 solution). The precipitate was dried at 150° for 1 h in an oven, and weighed. The results have been shown in Table 1.

Effect of diverse ions: Interference, in varying degrees, has been shown by Ag^+ , Hg^+ , Tl^+ , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Rh^{3+} , Pt^{4+} and Cr^{3+} in the experimental conditions of the determination. The removal of these ions, if present, is necessary before applying the above method.